

Table S5. Primers for used in the current study for amplification of three mitochondrial and two nuclear loci (All sequences from 5'-3' direction).

SL. No	Marker	Primer Name	Primer sequence	Fragment size	Reference
1	16s	16sa-l (F)	CGC CTG TTT ATC AAA AAC AT	570 bp	Palumbi <i>et al.</i> (1991); Hawlitschek <i>et al.</i> (2012)
		16sb- h (R)	CCG GTC TGA ACT CAG ATC ACG T		
2	12s	L1091 (F)	AAA AAG CTT CAA ACT GGG ATT AGA TAC CCC ACT AT	386 bp	Kocher <i>et al.</i> (1989); Rawling (2008)
		H1478 (R)	TGA CTG CAG AGG GTG ACG GGC GGT GTG T		
3	ND4	ND4 (F)	CAC CTA TGA CTA CCA AAA GCT CAT GTA GAA GC	488 bp	Arévalo <i>et al.</i> (1994)
		Leu (R)	CAT TAC TTT TAC TTG GAT TTG CAC CA		
4	c-mos	S77 (F)	CAT GGA CTG GGA TCA GTT ATG	576 bp	Lawson <i>et al.</i> (2005)
		S78 (R)	CCT TGG GTG TGA TTT TCT CAC CT		
5	PRLR	PRLR_f1	GAC ARY GAR GAC CAG CAA CTR ATG CC	555 bp	Townsend <i>et al.</i> (2008)
		PRLR_r3	GAC YTT GTG RAC TTC YAC RTA ATC CAT		